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DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN PRESCHOOL AGE

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ABSTRACT

The use of modern digital technologies is gaining relevance at all levels of education, including early education. Today children are surrounded by digital technologies, and therefore the digital "environment" is natural and much more understandable to them than it is to many of us. By the time they start kindergarten, children already have experience using a variety of digital technologies. Preschool children master computers and telephones faster and faster and it became their favorite work to do.

The use of traditional resources in early education and the neglect of technology for learning and play may no longer meet the needs and interests of children today.

KEYWORDS

Preschool education, self-expression, educational games, constructivism,
Digital technology

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Digital technologies offer children a variety of means and modalities for constructing knowledge and building skills. For studying and representing reality Smartphones, computers, and easily programmable gaming robots provide such opportunities, that would be unimaginable or very difficult without them. The connection between playing and learning has been the subject of debate among scientists for decades. It is considered an integral, closely interdependent process at an early age. Scaffolding, used by the teacher, turns the child's initiative into a learning opportunity, so that the form and process are maintained that are interesting to the child. Digital technologies are an important tool for encouraging exploration through play. New technologies allow us to experience multimodal, multiliteracy, technological competence, and also offer us means of self-expression in a variety of ways. Along with technological progress, imagination and play become stronger. Children of early age contribute to the development of memory, logical thinking and imagination, as well as the development of speech sound letter structure and mathematical knowledge. for preschool children demonstration of blocks of knowledge on the screen in an accessible form, such as multimedia, games - helps to attract attention, increases the level of educational motivation, creates excellent opportunities for individualization of education. It creates independence and self-confidence.

Technologies allow the teacher to implement an individual approach to each child at a new level, to increase children's motivation, movement, sound. Animation attracts children's attention for a long time and helps to increase their interest and motivation in the studied material. To ensure the clarity of the presentation of any material and to teach the prerequisites for independent acquisition of knowledge.

Today, children are the aborigines of the technological world. Often, surprisingly, they learn to use different types of technologies very easily, quickly and without too much effort and develop 21st century skills. technology is a field where children, from an early age, have the opportunity to demonstrate their competence and creativity. t may be harmful to the early development of children. In order to promote child development by using tecnology and not the other way around, it is important to consider two principles: limit the time for children with technologies and use the time allocated for children to have valuable and interesting experiences. Teachers and parents play an important role for that.The use of technology in a preschool institution will have a certain impact on the form of the educational process, including the interaction between children and the teacher: on the one hand, it will be additional control of children by the teacher during the use of technology (time period, relevance of content), and on the other hand - a deliberate effort by teachers to teach children Using different technologies, make this process a learning and developing experience.For kindergardens It is typical to consider the following main elements:

- A competent child who has many "languages" of learning and self-expression; Accordingly, the approach is based on following children's interests, in-depth research of events and subjects by children (long-term projects), creativity.
- Aesthetics as an important aspect of educational process and environment.
- The environment as a teacher.
- Documenting as a means of "saving" experience and re-analyzing.
- Community and shared culture as a pillar of knowledge acquisition and development.

There are pros and cons to using a computer at the preschool level:

through various websites, children can learn a lot of interesting material with the help of parent/teacher. for example: searching the pictures of favorite animals. Playing computer games with other children is helpful for learning to the rules and to see whose turn is now, also cooperation and mutual sharing of emotions. Many age-appropriate games contribute to the development of thinking, attention, memory, creative skills. Using a computer mouse, children develop fine motor skills and spatial orientation.

Disadvantages of the computer:

The child is not physically active while playing computer games. When a child plays alone with the computer, he does not develop social skills. Therefore, try to use computer games only when you are with other children. Attention should also be paid to the fact that the child is engaged in educational games and it should not be aggressive and violent.

Conclusion and recommendation:

- It is necessary for parents and teachers to keep an eye on the child when he is using the computer. This allows you to know what the child is doing always. Also what type of games he plays, how much time he spends using the computer, how dependent he is on the computer, and so on.

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